

An In-Depth Review of Literature on the Application of Optimization Methods in Estimating Parameters for Software Reliability Growth Models¹

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Abstract

The concept of software reliability relates to the probability that a piece of software will continue to operate without any malfunctions over a certain amount of time and in a given ecosystem. It is an essential component of the overall quality of the programme. It is a beneficial practice to evaluate the dependability of software at an early stage in the development life cycle. This is because it may save a significant amount of time and money by eliminating the need for major defect rectification after the product has been deployed. In light of the fact that businesses strive to offer software that is free of flaws, the evaluation of software dependability has emerged as a central focus of study. There are a great number of software reliability growth models available for the purpose of evaluating software reliability, which helps in the development of systems that are both robust and fault-tolerant. A comprehensive review of optimisation strategies that have been used by a variety of researchers in the process of improving software reliability growth models in order to accurately predict software dependability is presented in this study.

Keywords

Reliability, Optimization.

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Accepted: 01 December 2023 / Published online: 11 December 2023

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1. Introduction

The issue of developing software that is reliable has grown more difficult as software systems have become more complex, as they have been subjected to ever-changing requirements, and as they have adopted a distributed nature. The process of achieving reliability, which refers to the chance of software failure, is becoming more difficult. Failures in software may be traced back to a variety of factors, including mistakes, defective functionality, ambiguities, improper requirement analysis, inefficient code, insufficient testing, problems with timing, sequencing, data processing, and exception management. In the area of software quality, software dependability is an essential characteristic, along with other characteristics such as usability, performance, functionality, maintainability, stability, serviceability, documentation, and a number of other characteristics.[1]

The problems that occur with soft software may be broken down into the following categories:

- a) **Transient failures**, which occur for specific inputs,
- b) **Permanent failures**, which occur for all inputs,
- c) **Recoverable failures**, where the system can recover with or without operator intervention,
- d) **Unrecoverable failures**, which necessitate system restart,
- e) **Cosmetic failures**, causing minor irritations."

Each and every software development agreement mandates the inclusion of reliability standards. This is due to the fact that no software system can be completely free of errors. Software reliability models, which are statistical in nature, provide predictions about the failure rate of a software system by using the system's previous failure data as their basis. In order to shape the structure of the model and define its parameters, these models are based on assumptions about the process of locating and fixing errors. Following the determination of these characteristics and the identification of the current number of faults, it is possible to estimate the number of defects that are still present (see Figure 1).

When it comes to determining whether or not the code is ready to be sent, these residual faults perform a very important job. In addition to this, they provide an estimate of the amount of failures that

consumers are likely to have when using the programme. After the programme has been deployed, this information is helpful in determining the needed support levels as well as the related cost of assistance for the rectification of defects.

Software reliability modeling techniques can be broadly divided into two main categories [3]:

a) **Prediction models:** These models make use of past data in order to forecast dependability, and they are often carried out before the stages of development or testing come into play. Both planning and sensitivity analysis are aided by their assistance. The shortcut model, the full-scale model, the Rayleigh model, and the Neufelder assessment model are some examples [4]. Many more models are also examples.

b) **Estimation models:** In order to estimate dependability throughout the system-level testing or operational stages, these models make use of data obtained from the current software development process. The failure rate, also known as the Mean Time Between Failure (MTBF), may be predicted with their assistance. Models such as the Goel-Okumoto model, the Weibull model, the S-shaped model, and others are illustrations of this.

Fig 2: Types of Reliability Models

In order to ensure that the Software Reliability Growth Model (SRGM) operates in an accurate manner, it is essential to accurately determine the characteristics of software reliability. The degree of precision with which parameters are measured is directly related to the degree of accuracy that the SRGM has. In light of this, there is a need for a procedure that can estimate these factors in software dependability in the most effective manner. One of the goals of optimisation as a method is to attain optimum performance by maximising the qualities that are wanted and minimising the aspects that are not desired. The purpose of this work is to investigate the many optimisation strategies that researchers have used in order to improve the precision of parameter estimates in software reliability growth models. This will eventually result in a more accurate evaluation of software reliability.

2. Software Reliability Growth Models

In the testing phase, a reliability growth model is used to determine how the system's dependability develops over time. This is done in order to ensure consistent performance. Software Reliability Growth Models, also known as SRGM, are statistical models that make use of mathematical functions to discover flaws. These models are capable of assisting in the prediction of failure rates or residual faults [5]. The concave and S-shaped models are the two kinds of reliability growth models that are frequently described in this context.

Data in the software reliability growth model is categorized as follows [6]:

- a) **Test Time Data:** This includes calendar time, execution time, and the number of test runs.
- b) **Defect Data:** This comprises major defect data, which can be tolerated for a certain period, and critical defect data, which requires an immediate solution.
- c) **Grouped Data:** This involves a combination of test time and the quantity of detected failures.

2.1 Software Reliability Modeling Process

- a) **Examination of Data:** This step involves plotting data over time and analyzing the collected information.
- b) **Model Selection:** The choice of the model is based on the available data, the testing process, and assumptions related to the model.
- c) **Parameter Estimation:** This step involves utilizing statistical functions such as the least square method or maximum likelihood for estimating parameters.
- d) **Obtaining Fitted Model:** This includes substituting the estimated parameters into the selected model.
- e) **Evaluation of Fitness:** A goodness-of-fit test is conducted to assess whether the chosen model is appropriate.

f) **Reliability Predictions:** Predictions of reliability are made based on the selected model.

2.2 Examples of software reliability growth models:

Table 1: Software Reliability Growth Models and their prediction functions

Software Reliability Growth Model	$\mu(t)$
G-O Model	$a(1 - e^{-bt})$
Delayed S- shaped model	$a(1 - (1 + bt)e^{-bt})$
Weibull model	$a(1 - e^{-bt})^\alpha$
M-O model	$a \ln(1+bt)$
JM model	$N(1 - \exp(-\phi t))$

2.3 Factors affecting the performance of Software Reliability Growth Models [7]

- Unsolved problematic issues
- Complexity of the reliability models
- The Misconception of fault and failure phenomena
- Unfounded types of assumptions
- Inaccurate modeling parameters
- Difficulty in selecting the reliability models
- Weakness of the reliability model
- Complexity of the software

3. Optimization Techniques

- Cuckoo Search:** Inspired by the brood parasite behavior of cuckoo birds, this technique introduces new and improved solutions, represented as cuckoo eggs, into the existing nest of solutions. These eggs are modifications of the current characteristics, aiming to enhance the overall solution [8].
- Ant Colony:** Drawing inspiration from the pheromone trail behavior of ants, this technique follows paths with stronger pheromone concentrations, resulting in the adoption of the shortest paths by more ants [8].
- Firefly Optimization:** Mimicking the communication and signaling behavior of fireflies, this technique attracts fireflies with brighter flashes, representing improved solutions [9].
- Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO):** The particles wander around the search space, assessing their best placements in each iteration and converging towards the global best solution. This behaviour is modelled after the natural behaviour of fish schools and bird flocks.
- Grey Wolf:** This method divides the wolf population into four distinct groups: alpha, beta, delta, and omega. The classification is based on the hunting behaviour of grey wolves. In order to discover the most effective solutions, the optimisation process is structured similarly to the hierarchy, with the leaders (alpha, beta, and delta) serving as guides.

f) **Bee Colony Optimization:** Artificial bees explore the search space, constructing and refining solutions. Afterward, bees return to the hive, share information about their solutions, and decide whether to continue exploration or become recruiters or followers [8].

4. Related Work

Sheta and Raouf [10] employed “the grey wolf optimizing algorithm to estimate parameters for three software reliability growth models: exponential, power, and S-shaped. Their methodology successfully estimated parameters, demonstrating efficacy on real test/debug datasets”.

Jin and Wei-Jin [11] utilized “the quantum particle swarm optimization (QPSO) algorithm for optimizing parameters in a reliability model. The proposed model, with optimized parameters, outperformed existing models on various software failure datasets”.

Saati and Marwa [12] used “Cuckoo Search for estimating parameters of software reliability growth models and found it outperformed Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) and Ant Colony Optimization (ACO)”.

Choudhary et al. [13] applied “the firefly algorithm for effective parameter estimation in software reliability growth models, showcasing superiority over other techniques”.

Bidhan and Awashti [14] employed Particle Swarm Optimization to evaluate growth models, yielding optimized results and overcoming issues faced by traditional estimation methods.

Mallikharjuna and Anuradha [15] used a “Modified Genetic Swarm Optimization algorithm to optimize parameters in software reliability growth models, demonstrating effectiveness compared to Genetic Algorithm (GA) and Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO)”.

Malhotra and Negi [16] proposed using particle swarm optimization (PSO) for software reliability growth models parameter estimation, showcasing high predictive ability.

Mallikharjuna and Auradha [17] “applied artificial bee colony optimization for parameter estimation in software reliability growth models, significantly improving reliability growth”.

Zheng et al. [18] suggested “Ant Colony Optimization for estimating software reliability, showing superior accuracy compared to traditional methods and nearly ten times higher accuracy for some models”.

Shanmugam and Florence [19] utilized “Ant Colony Algorithm for parameter estimation in software reliability growth models, achieving higher precision, faster convergence, and increased accuracy”.

5. Conclusion

In the realm of software quality, reliability is an essential component that plays a significant role in defining trustworthiness and contributing to the creation of resilient systems. There are many different software growth models that estimate reliability, and it is possible to improve forecasts of failure rates or residual defects by parameter optimisation. The purpose of this research was to examine several optimisation strategies, such as ant colony, bee colony, grey wolf, firefly, and particle swarm, and to demonstrate the simplicity of computing and effectiveness of these strategies. The efficiency of

optimisation approaches in software reliability growth model parameter estimation was shown by the fact that they regularly beat older methods..

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